

AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF CUSTOMER COMPLAINT MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN THE SMART PHONE INDUSTRY: A CASE STUDY OF UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA.

¹Aniebiet J Etuk, ²Aniekan Eyo Awah and ³Aniefiok Okon Akpan

¹Department of Marketing, Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus¹

^{2,3}Department of Marketing, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

E-mail: aniekaneawah@uniuyo.edu.ng.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13991688>

Abstract: *The objective of this study was to examine the influence of customer complaint management on customer satisfaction of smart phone industry in Akwa Ibom State. To achieve this objective, the main source of data was through primary sources with the use of a questionnaire. The researcher adopted the survey research design approach and data were collected from 368 respondents drawn from the smart phone customers' base. A total number of 322 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved in useable form representing 87.3 percent of data analyzed using the Simple Regression Model (SRM). Data generated from the study were processed using descriptive and inferential statistics and hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that customer complaint management had significant influence on customer satisfaction of Smart Phones industry in Akwa Ibom State. Thus, the study recommended that the managers of smart phone firms should establish and implement structured complaint management systems that facilitate prompt responses to customer grievances. These systems should include clear protocols for receiving, tracking and resolving complaints efficiently.*

Keywords: *Customer Complaint Management Systems, Customer Satisfaction, Smart Phone Industry.*

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

In an era characterized by rapid technological advancements and intense market competition, the smart phone industry has emerged as a pivotal sector influencing communication, commerce and everyday life (Statista, 2023). With increasing consumer expectations and an overwhelming variety of

brands and models, customer satisfaction has become a crucial determination of success for smart phone manufacturers and retailers (Yasemin and Bansal, 2022; Etuk, Awah and Akpan, 2024).

Customer complaint management plays a significant role in shaping consumer perceptions and experiences. Effective management of complaints can lead to enhanced customer loyalty, positive brand reputations and ultimately increased profitability (Davidow, 2021; Etuk, Akpan and Awah, 2022). However, the high incidence of complaints in the smart phone sector often stemming from product defects, service delivery issues and unmet expectations necessitates a comprehensive approach to understanding and addressing these concerns (Nichalas, et. al., 2022).

Customer complaint is an expression of dissatisfaction from a customer regarding a product, service or purchasing experience (Olarunleke, 2022). Tronvoll (2012) calls It a formal or informal customer report regarding a problem with a product or service. Research has shown that, the way a company handles company complaints can affect its business success in the long term (Robert-Lombard, 2011). Gelbrich & Roschk (2010) assert that poor complaint handling procedures could damage company-customer relationship and cause customer dissatisfaction. It could promote negative word of mouth advertising causing potential customers to refrain from doing business with the company. It could cause low customer loyalty and significantly affect customer retention. Awara (2010) opines that poor customer complaints handling ultimately cause companies to lose customers thereby losing market share, whilst the recruiting of new customers through marketing promotions cost money, effectively reducing company profitability.

In Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, the smart phone market has witnessed exponential growth, fueled by a burgeoning youth population and increasing digital literacy (Nigerian Communication Commissions, 2023). Despite this growth, many smart phones retailers struggle with effectively managing customer complaints, leading to dissatisfaction and potential loss of customers. This situation highlights the need for an in-depth investigation into how complaint management practices influence overall customer satisfaction within this specific context (Ali & Muthusamy, 2023).

This study aims to explore the influence of customer complaint management systems on customer satisfaction in the smart phone industry in Uyo Metropolis; by analyzing existing frameworks and identifying best practices, this research seeks to contribute to the understanding of how effective complaint resolution can enhance customer loyalty and improve business outcomes (Ladhari, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

Despite the rapid growth of the smart phone industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, many retailers struggle to effectively manage customer complaints. This deficiency has resulted in a significant number of dissatisfied customers, impacting overall brand perception and customer loyalty.

In a highly competitive market, the failure to address customer grievances promptly and effectively can lead to negative word-of-mouth, decreased customer retention and a potential decline in sales. Existing literature suggests that effective complaint management can transform negative experiences

into opportunities for building stronger customer relationships, however, the application of these principles in the local context of Uyo remains unexplored.

Furthermore, the lack of structured complaint management systems among smart phones retailers may hinder their ability to respond to customer needs effectively thereby exacerbating dissatisfaction and limiting the potential for brand loyalty. This study seeks to investigate the gap in understanding how the management of customer complaints influences customer satisfaction in the smart phone sector, aiming to provide insight that can help retailers enhance their complaint resolution processes and improve overall customer experiences.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the influence of customer complaint management systems on customer satisfaction of selected smart phones industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives therefore include to;

- i. determine the influence of ease of prompt response to complaints on customer satisfaction of smart phones industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. examine the influence of complaint lodging on customer satisfaction of smart phones industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

1.3 Research Questions

This study attempts to provide answers to the following research questions.

- i. What is the influence of prompt response to complaints on customer satisfaction of smart phones industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State?
- ii. What is the influence of ease of complaint lodging on customer satisfaction of smart phones industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were postulated to guide the study:

- i. Prompt response to complaints does not significantly influence customer satisfaction of smart phones industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. Ease of complaint lodging does not significantly influence customer satisfaction of smart phones industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study holds considerable significance for multiple stakeholders within the smart phones industry and beyond. By examining the influence of customer complaint management on customer satisfaction, this research will provide actionable insights for smart phone retailers and manufacturers. Understanding effective complaint resolutions strategies can enhance customer loyalty and improve overall business performance. Retailers can adopt best practices identified in this study to create a more responsive customer service framework.

The findings of this study will benefit consumers by highlighting the importance of their feedback in shaping service quality. As customers become aware of their influence on complaint management practices, they may be encouraged to provide constructive feedback, ultimately leading to enhanced customer service and satisfaction in the smart phone market.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The scope of the study covered the following three central aspects:

Content Scope: The content scope of this study covers the consumer complaint management variables used by smart phones industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State such as, ease of complaint lodging, prompt response to complaints and customer satisfaction. It covers concept on consumer complaint management variables as related to customer satisfaction. This study was domicile in service marketing.

Geographical Scope: The geographical scope of the study was in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State located at the South-South region of Nigeria.

Unit of Analysis: The unit of analysis of this study involves customers of smart phones in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Concept of Complaint Management

A customer complaint is when a customer expresses dissatisfaction or issues with a product, service or experience they had with a firm. Complaints can be about anything from product quality to customer service or billing errors. Handling these complaints effectively is crucial for businesses to maintain customer satisfaction and improve their offerings (Oru and Madumere, 2022). According to Agu (2014), a complaint is defined as an expression of dissatisfaction directed to an organization concerning its product or the process of handling complaints, with the expectation of receiving a response or resolution, either explicitly or implicitly expected.

Customer complaint management is a critical aspect of customer service and relationship management for businesses across various industries. It involves systematic process of receiving, recording, investigating and resolving complaints or grievances raised by customers regarding products, services or experiences with smart phones. Effective complaint management not only addresses the immediate issue but also plays a crucial role in maintaining customer loyalty, reputation management and overall business success (Oranusi, Nwaizugbo, Okolo, Obikeze and Ikpo, 2021).

Complaint management refers to the structured approach organizations use to handle and resolve customers grievances. It involves several key steps;

1. Receipt and Recording: Complaint are collected and documented systematically to ensure no issue is overlooked (Smith and Chang,2023).
2. Investigation; The organization investigates the complaint to understand the root cause and context of the issue (Lee, 2022).
3. Resolution: Solutions or compensations are provided to address the customer’s concern and resolve the problem (Johnson, 2023).
4. Feedback and Improvement; Organizations analyze complaint to identify patterns and areas for improvement, thereby preventing future issues and enhancing overall service quality (Brown and Peter, 2023).
5. Follow-Up: Ensuring that the customer is satisfied with the resolution and maintaining ongoing communication to rebuild trust (Wang et. al., 2024).

The Commonwealth Ombudsman in Agu (2014) identified the following steps of effective management of customer complaints:

- Acknowledge all complaints quickly
- Assess the complaint and give it priority
- Plan the investigation
- Investigate the complaint
- Respond to the complaint with a clear decision
- Follow up any customers service issues
- Consider if there are any systemic issues.

The guide equally identified five principles of effective complaint handling as fairness, accessibility, responsiveness, efficiency and integration. Effective complaint management benefits an organization in the following ways:

- It identifies areas that need to be changed and allows clients to provide input to service improvement.
- It gives the organization a second change to serve and satisfy dissatisfied clients.
- It provides an opportunity to strengthen public support for the organization.
- It helps reduce an organization’s workload.
- Improves customers loyalty
- enhances word-of-mouth promotion
- Ensure Long-term profitability.

Effective complaint management not only resolves individual issues but also contributes long –term customer satisfaction and loyalty by demonstrating responsiveness and commitment to quality.

Iyadi (2023) investigated the relationship between customer complaint handling strategies and customer retention; evidence from bakery sub-sector of food processing industry in Nigeria revealed a significant relationship between the complaint handling techniques employed by the selected baking

firms and customer retention. They concluded that achieving customer attention in the bakery sector depended on how well customer complaints were managed, a finding supported by their study's result. Handling complaints affect client retention and revenue, a satisfied consumer will tell five of their closest friends about an issue fixed compared to three if the service was initially good (Johnson,2021; Etuk, Awah and Akpan, 2024). If the first service was bad and not remedied, the unsatisfied client will notify 10-20 individuals. Unreliable service, poor employee attitude and complicated information design caused dissatisfaction (Tronvill and Hokinpuro,2021). Customers/consumers complained to the service provider following service failures. When services fell short, customers grumbled and became dissatisfied. Consequently, unsatisfied customers complained more than satisfied ones. The ability of smart phone firms to prevent, resolve and share solutions for complaints is crucial in handling complaints (Iyadi and Christopher,2022).

2.1.2 Concept of Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction refers to the degree to which a customer's expectations and needs are met by a company's products or services. Effective customer complaint management is crucial in maintaining and enhancing this satisfaction. It involves handling customer complaints effectively and efficiently, addressing their concerns and taking corrective action to prevent future issues ((Brown and Peter, 2023)

Recent research emphasizes the importance of integrating customer complaint management into overall customer satisfaction strategies. For instance: Zeitham, Bitner and Gremier (2020) in their study on services marketing: Integrating customer focus across the firm. This study discussed how complaint management was crucial to customer retention and satisfaction, noting that the way complaints were handled could significantly impact customer perceptions and loyalty. McCole (2021) in their study on the role of customer complaints in the service recovery process explored how effective complaint management contributed to improved customer satisfaction and loyalty by analyzing different service recovery strategies. Davidow (2023) in their study on the impact of service failures and recovery on customer loyalty. This study provided insights into how handling customer complaints appropriately could mitigate negative effects and even enhance overall customer satisfaction. These studies illustrated that efficient complaint management not only resolved issues but also served as an opportunity to strengthen customer relationships and improve overall satisfaction.

2.1.3 The Relationship between Prompt Response to Complaints and Customer Satisfaction

Prompt response to complaint refers to the timely and effective handling of customer grievances. It is a key complaint management tool and is closely linked to customer satisfaction. A prompt response ensures that issues are addresses quickly, reducing customer frustration and demonstrating the company's commitment to customer care. Recent research studies underscore the importance of

prompt responses in enhancing customer satisfaction. Zeithaml, Bitner and Gremler (2020) in their study emphasized that timely responses to customer complaints are essential for maintaining customer satisfaction. They discussed how quick resolution of issues not only alleviate immediate customer dissatisfaction but also fosters a positive perception of the company's customer service. McCole (2021) in their study highlighted that prompt responses to complaints are critical in the service recovery process. The research findings of this study revealed that quick and effective handling of complaints can significantly improve customer satisfaction and loyalty, as it demonstrates the company's responsiveness and dedication to resolving issues. Davidow (2023) in their study on the impact of service failures and recovery on customer loyalty provided insights into how the speed of response affects customer loyalty. The study found that customers who receive a swift and effective resolution to their complaints are more likely to remain satisfied and loyal, as prompt responses are perceived as a sign of effective service and customer-centricity.

Oru and Madumere (2022) investigated the influence of customer complaint management on marketing performance of banks found out that there was a significant influence of prompt responsiveness to complaint on marketing performance of banks. They opined that banks were encouraged to respond timely to complaints as this would result in greater satisfaction and advocacy among customers.

These studies collectively illustrate that prompt responses to complaint are a crucial factor in customer satisfaction. By addressing issues quickly, smart phone companies can prevent escalation of dissatisfaction and reinforce positive customer relationships.

2.1.4 The Relationship between Ease of Complaint Lodging and Customer Satisfaction

Ease of complaint lodging refers to how simple and straightforward it is for customers to file a complaint or express dissatisfaction with a product or service. When linked with customer satisfaction, it emphasizes that a more accessible and user-friendly complaint process can enhance overall customer satisfaction. This is because customers feel their issues are taken seriously and can be addressed more efficiently, leading to a better overall experience with the company (Oru and Madumere, 2022).

Davidow (2003) sees it as the simplicity and accessibility of the process for customers to file grievances or concerns. A streamlined process allows customers to voice their issues with minimal effort, which is crucial for maintaining their satisfaction and loyalty. A simple complaint process can enhance customer trust and transparency. When customers can easily report problems, they feel the company is open to feedback and is committed to addressing issues (Tax, Brown and Chandrashekar, 1998).

Quick and easy complaint lodging often leads to faster resolution, which is directly linked to higher customer satisfaction. When customers see that their issues are resolved efficiently, their overall experience with the service or product improves (Smith, Bolton and Wagner, 1999). Tax, Brown and

Chandrashekar (1998) in their study on customer evaluations of service complaint experiences: Implications for relationship marketing discussed the role of complaint handling in customer relationships, underlining the significance of ease of complaint process. Smith, Bolton and Wagner (1999) in their study on a model of customer satisfaction with service encounters involving failures and recovery found out that ease of complaint lodging has significant influence on customer satisfaction. These studies provide a foundation for understanding how the ease of lodging complaints correlates with customer satisfaction, highlighting both theoretical and practical aspects.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

In this section one major theory was considered relevant for this study; they include;

2.2.1. Attribution Theory

The theory adopted in this study is the attribution theory. It provides marketers with guidance on how to deal with potential or existing perception of consumer dissatisfaction. If the cause of the dissatisfaction actually is permanent, market-related and under the marketer's control, something must be done to correct the problem or provide the consumer with restitution.

Heider (1958) was the first proponent of attribution theory; while Weiner and colleagues developed a theoretical framework that has become a major research paradigm of social psychology (www.instructionaldesign.org) assessed (2019). Attribution theory is concerned with how individuals interpret events and how these relate to their thinking and behavior. It assures that people try to know why people do what they do i.e. attribute causes to behavior. Attribution theory explains how individuals think about explanations for or causes of effects or behavior, when a product or services does not fulfill consumers' needs, individuals will attempt to find an explanation based on three factors.

- Stability: Is the cause of the event temporary or permanent?
- Focus: is the problem customer or marketer related?
- Controllability: Is the event under the customers or marketer's control?

Attribution theory also applies to service. Customers who can choose whether to participate in a service are likely to attribute at least part of the negative outcome to their own involvement. They will also attribute a good part of any positive outcome to their own participation (Benda Pudi and Leone, 2003: 14-28) quoted in Hoyer and Macinnis (2008: 283). Satisfaction with services also depends on whether the consumer holds the company responsible for the outcome and believes the outcome stems from a stable or unstable cause (Tsiros, Mittal and Ross, 2004: 476-483) in Hoyer and Macinnis, 2008: 283). Finally, consumers are more satisfied when companies exert extra effort to serve them, even when the offerings are not great (Morale 2005) quoted in Hoyer and Macinnis (2008: 283).

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

This section is concerned with the review of the studies which were considered to be relevant,

International Journal of Management Communication(IJMC)

<https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/IJMC/index>, Email: contact@americaserial.com

accordingly, 6 studies were reviewed.

2.3.1 Ogunu, Nwokah and Acee-Eke (2019): Examined the influence of procedural justice on customer post-complaint behavior in Fast food firms in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. They adopted /Descriptive and inferential statistics analysis for data analysis. The study findings revealed that procedural justice was not positively related to repeat purchase, word of mouth and commitment.

They concluded that effective and efficient service delivery anchored on sound grasp of customers' needs matched with appropriate distributive justice would enhance good post complaint behaviour. They recommended that fast food business should adopt policies such as robust customer collaborative, market intelligence as a means of reassuring customers of super value proposition in their service delivery.

2.3.2 Iyadi (2023): Investigated the influence of customer complaint handling strategies on customer retention in the Nigerian bakery sub- sector of food processing industry. The specific objectives of the study were to examined the influence of compensation on customer retention in the bakery sector, the influence of service quality on customer retention in the bakery sector and the influence of timely response on customer retention in the bakery sector. The researcher adopted descriptive and inferential statistics analysis for data analysis. The study findings revealed a significant relationship between the complaint handling techniques used by the selected bakery firms and customer retention. The study concluded that the achievement of customer retention in the bakery sector depended on the extent customer complaint were well managed which the outcome of their research has demonstrated. They recommended that the food processing sector should make provision for compensation of customers based on poor services.

2.3.3 Oru and Madumere (2022): Conducted a study on the influence of customer complaint management on marketing performance of banks. They adopted simple regression analysis for data analysis. The findings of the study showed that the customer complaint based on management constructs (accessibility, responsiveness, integration) significantly influence marketing performance of bank. The study therefore recommended that banks should design complaint management systems that are simple and understandable for customers, while being fair, efficient, and responsive in complaint handling.

2.3.4 Salim, Setiawan, Rofiaty and Rohman (2018): Studied the effect of customer complaints handling and the quality of bank services on customer loyalty to public sector banks owned by the government in Jakarta, Indonesia. They adopted descriptive and inferential statistics analysis for data analysis. The findings of the study revealed that the quality of the service has a positive effect on satisfaction, but the quality of service did not affect customer loyalty.

Customer complaints had a positive effect on satisfaction, but the handling of customer complaints had no effect on customer loyalty. The customer satisfaction had a positive effect on customer loyalty. The result of mediation path hypothesis testing showed that the influence of service quality on

customer loyalty was mediated by customer satisfaction showing positive relationship. The influence of complaints on customer loyalty was mediated by customer satisfaction showing a positive relationship also.

Complaint handling had the greatest coefficient value in creating customer satisfaction and impacting customer loyalty. The study therefore recommended that bank must try to find the root of the problem of any failure and error of a service, so then the company can formulate the best solution to any problems / complaints that arise. One of the advantages of learning from service mistakes from the past is that companies can anticipate service failures in the future.

2.3.5 Olurunlere (2022): Studied the influence of customer's complaint management on customer satisfaction of banks in Akure, Ondo. They adopted descriptive and inferential statistics analysis for data analysis. The findings of the study revealed that complaints handling practices had significant effect on the performance of Deposit Money Banks in Ondo State, Nigeria. The study therefore recommended that a well-organized Complaints handling Practices provides direction towards goal attainment and improvement of performance.

2.3.6 Oranusi, Nwaizugbo, Okolo, Obikeze, Ikpo and Ogbodo (2021): Examined the impact of customer complaints and feedback management on customer retention in Deposit money banks in South-Eastern, Nigeria. They adopted descriptive and inferential statistics analysis for data analysis. The findings of the study showed that customer complaints management had a significant positive relationship with customer retention in deposit money banks in South-Eastern Nigeria. Similarly, it was revealed that customer feedback management had a significant positive relationship with customer retention in deposit money banks in South-Eastern Nigeria. Thus, the study recommended that customer complaints and feedback management strategies are very efficacious marketing strategies for ensuring customer retention in the Nigerian banking industry.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Design of the Study

The study design adopted by the researcher in this study was the survey research design. Data on the two independent variables and the dependent variable were collected from different smart phone firms in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. The survey research design used assisted the researcher in reaching out to a good number of customers of the smart phone firms throughout Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

3.2 Population of the Study

The target population for this study comprise of all the customers of smart phone firms in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Hence, the target population for this study was infinite.

3.3 Sampling and the Sample Size determination

Since the population size for the study was infinite, sample size for this study was determined using the Topman Formula at 5% level of tolerable error.

The formula is given as

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot pq}{e^2}$$

Where n = required sample size

z = the value of z-score associated with the degree of confidence is 95% confidence level being 1.96 from the Z-score table.

p = 0.3 decimal (positive)

q = 0.7 decimal (negative)

e = acceptable tolerance level of error (stated in percentage points)

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{Z^2 \cdot pq}{e^2} \\ &= \frac{1.96^2 \cdot (0.4 \times 0.6)}{0.05^2} \\ &= \frac{3.8416 \times 0.24}{0.0025} \\ &= \frac{0.921984}{0.0025} \\ &= 368.7 \\ &= 369 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the sample size of the study was 369.

3.4 Sampling Procedure

Convenient sampling technique was employed in the administration of the research instrument for this study. This was carried out by reaching out to the respondents based on their willingness to participate in the research as well as their accessibility and availability to the researcher. The researcher clearly explained the purpose of the research, the time commitment required and how the research data will be used helped in understanding and improving respondents' willingness to participate.

3.5 Methods of Data Collection

Data analysis involved both descriptive and inferential statistics. Data was analyzed using the simple regression analysis to determine the influence of customer complaint management on customer satisfaction. All hypotheses were tested at $P > 0.05$ level of significance.

3.6 Sources of Data

The main source of data employed in this study was the primary data source. The primary data source was a structured questionnaire which was served on respondents. The questionnaire was made up of two sections: section "A" generated data on demography, while section "B" was made up of two sub-sections which were the independent variables (ease of complaint lodging, prompt response to

complaint and the dependent variable (customer satisfaction). Hence, the ordinal scale used for this study were strongly agree, 4; agree,3; disagree,2; strongly disagree,1; neutral,0; to elicit responses from the respondents. The five points were employed to measure the dependent and the independent variables.

3.7 Validity of the Instrument

The research instrument was subjected to validity test by experts in the field of study. The relevance of each item in relation to the purpose of the study and the formulated hypotheses was assessed independently by these experts. Then the researcher used all the other observations made by these experts in preparing the final copy of the questionnaire.

3.8 Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the research instrument was conducted to ascertain the degree to which the instrument yields consistent result. Hence, it was conducted to ascertain whether the variables of the study consistently measured the factors intended. In this study the internal consistency reliability was adopted, a pre-test for internal consistency measure using Cronbach's Alpha was employed for assessing the reliability of the research instrument. The purpose of reliability test was to further ascertain whether the internal consistency of the scales is indicative of the homogeneity of the construct items that measures the variables. In the process, the reliability for each of these scales was determined at a minimum threshold of 0.7 and above (Cronbach,1951).

The obtained coefficients were

S/No	NO.of items	Study Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
------	-------------	-----------------	------------------

- | | | | |
|----|---|------------------------------|-------|
| 1. | 5 | Ease of Complaint Lodging | 0.851 |
| 2. | 4 | Prompt Response to Complaint | 0.774 |
| 3. | 6 | Customer Satisfaction | 0.782 |
-

Source Author's computation (2024)

In this study, the Cronbach alpha for all the construct ranges from 0.774 to 0.851. All the constructs had Cronbach Alpha greater than 0.70 thresholds which suggest that the instrument used for the evaluation was reliable. (Cronbach's Alpha > 0.70).

3.8 Instrument Administration

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire with a 5-point Likert Scale ranging from 5 (Strongly agreed) to 1 (Strongly disagree). This consisted of Section A and Section B. Section A presented respondents personal data such as the age distribution of the respondents ranging from 18 to 50 years and above, gender distribution of the respondents divided into male and female, educational level segmented into SSCE, Diploma, HND/B.Sc, Masters and Ph.D, marital status of the

respondents made up of single, married and divorced while section B presented questions on Prompt response to complaint, Ease of complaint lodging and customer satisfaction.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Data Analysis

Test of Hypothesis One

Prompt response to complaints does not significantly influence customer satisfaction of smart phones industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4.6 Model Summary of the Influence of Prompt Response to Complaint on Customer Satisfaction of Smart Phones Industry

Model R R Square Adjusted R Square Std.Error of the Estimate			
1	.819 ^a	.753	.731 .81270
a. Predictors (constant), Prompt Response to Complaint Source: Field Survey, 2024			
Analysis of Variance of the Influence of Prompt Response to Complaint on Customer Satisfaction of Smart Phones Industry			
Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square F Sig.
Regression	1214.751	1	1732.797 2027.365 .000 ^b
1 Residual	573.803	321	.781
Total	1787.554	322	

a. **Dependent Variable:** Customer Satisfaction

b. **Predictors:** (Constant), Prompt Response to Complaint

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The regression in table 4.6 shows that the coefficient of the constant terms (that is, the explanatory or predictor) variable. Prompt Response to Complaint has a R-value of (.819) which indicate a positive relationship between the explanatory variable and the criteria variable. The R-square, the coefficient of determination value is (.753). This means that 75.3 percent of the variation on the Customer Satisfaction can be explained from the independent variable (Prompt Response to Complaint). The table also shows the adjusted R-square for the model as (.731). But adjusted R-square is very useful in multiple regression analysis where it adjusts the R-square by the number of predictor values in the model. This adjustment allows the easy comparison of the explanatory power of the models with different numbers of independent variables. The F-ratio in the ANOVA table shows the overall regression effect in the model. The F-ratio value is 2027.365 which is significant at 0.000 and is less than 0.05 percent level of significance. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept that Prompt Response to Complaint contribute towards Customer Satisfaction in the smart phone industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis 2

Ease of complaint lodging does not significantly influence customer satisfaction of smart phone industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4.7: Model Summary of the Influence of Ease of Complaint Lodging on the Customer Satisfaction of selected of Smart Phones Industry

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.827	.893	.838	84262	
a. Predictors: (Constant), Ease of Complaint Lodging					
Analysis of Variance of the Influence of Ease of Complaint Lodging on the Customer Satisfaction of Smart Phones Industry					
Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	1853.241	1	1764.121	2681.379	.000 ^b
1 Residual	261.431	321	.727		
Total	2114.672	322			

a. **Dependent Variable:** Ease of Complaint Lodging

b. **Predictors:** (Constant), Customer Satisfaction

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The regression result in table 4.7 revealed that the regression coefficient of R-value is (.827) which indicates that there is a strong positive relationship existing between Ease of Complaint Lodging and Customer Satisfaction in the smart phone industry. The model summary table shows that the R-Square regression coefficient is (.893), which indicate that Ease of Complaint Lodging accounts for 89.3 percent of the total variation on the Customer Satisfaction of smart phone industry. The ANOVA table shows the F-ratio for the regression model which indicates the statistical significance of the overall regression model. The F-ratio value is 2681.379 which is statistically significance at 0.000 level. Since the probability value (P-V=0.000) is less than 0.05 percent, we reject the null hypothesis and upheld the alternative. This means that there is a significant effect of Ease of Complaint Lodging on Customer Satisfaction of smart phone industry.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary

The main thrust of this study has been presented in the preceding four sections. This section is concerned with the summary of major findings. The study investigated the influence of customer complaint management on customer satisfaction in smart phone industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State?

Two hypotheses were formulated to guide this study and all the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance through the use of simple regression analysis.

The two null hypotheses were rejected and the alternative hypotheses accepted. This resulted from the

fact that the regression results were all significant, the computed F-values for all the two hypotheses show statistical significance of the overall regression model, this means that there was statistically significant influence of Customer Complaint Management strategies such as (Prompt Response to Complaint and Ease of Complaint Lodging) on Customer Satisfaction of smart phone industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

To achieve the objectives, a survey research design was used to reach out to the respondents of the smart phone industry. The population of the study was infinite. The Topman sample size determination formula at 5% level of tolerable error was used to determine the sample size of 369. The convenience sampling technique was employed in the administration of the research instrument for the study.

5.2 Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were established.

1. Prompt response to complaint has significant influence on customer satisfaction of smart phone industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
2. Ease of complaint lodging has significant influence on customer satisfaction of smart phone industry in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, we recommend that the managers of the smart phone firms should enhance effective use of complaint management systems strategies to:

- 1) Establish and implement structured complaint management systems that facilitate prompt responses to customer grievances. These systems should include clear protocols for receiving, tracking and resolving complaints efficiently.
- 2) Develop user-friendly online platforms or mobile applications that facilitate easy complaint lodging features such as simple forms, clear instructions and a straight forward user interface can enhance the customer experience

REFERENCES

- Agodi, J. E., Aniekan E. A., and Oladipupo, A. (2016). Determinants of customers' patronage of fast-food restaurants in Umuahia, Abia State, Nigeria; *Journal of Economic Research and Entrepreneurship Development*. ISSN 9876- 5432: vol. 2, No. 2.
- Agodi, J. E., Ahaiwe, E. O., Awah, A. E. (2017). Salesman's personality Trait and its Effects on sales performance: Study of Fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) in Abia State, Nigeria, *international Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development* Vol. 8, No. 24.

International Journal of Management Communication

Volume 12 Issue 4, October-December 2024

ISSN: 2836-5844

Impact Factor: 5.58

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/IJMC/index>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Agodi, J.E., Kalu, A.O. and Awah, A.E. (2021). Impact of service recovery on customer loyalty of selected SMEs in Abia State, Nigeria, *Journal of Business Administration and Management Science, Alex Ekwueme Federal University, 1(1), 143-150*

Ali, A. and Muthusamy, S. (2023). Customer satisfaction and loyalty in the smart phone industry: An empirical analysis, *international journal of market research, 65(2), 158-176*.

Akpan, A. B. and Abdul, Z. (2009). Assessment of the impact of the of automated teller machine (ATM) on customer satisfaction the Nigerian banking industry, *Academy International journal of Nigeria, International headquarters, Ahmadu Bello university, Zaria, Nigeria,1(1),64-76*.

Akpan, A. B. (2007). Effective of bank capitalization and confidence: An assessment of customers perception in Nigeria, *Abuja journal of business administration, University of Abuja, Nigeria,1(2),96-110*.

Attih. O., Ikpe, I. and Mfon, A. (2017). Service marketing: A review. Akwa. Ibom. State. University (Aksu) *journal of management sciences, 2(1),19-22*.

Attih, O. B. (2020). Packaging attributes and consumer patronage of beverages in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *British journal of marketing studies, 8(6), 1-18*.

Awah, A.E., Mfon, A. A and Ibok, N.I. (2024). Celebrity endorsement and consumer buying behavior of Generation Y: A case study of select betting business in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. *Advance Journal of Economics, 9(1), 1-14*

Awah, A. E., Akpan, A. O. and Emmanuel, D. O. (2024). Service quality dimension and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Advance Journal of Economics and Marketing Research,9(2), 2-22*.

Awah, A. E., Akpan, A. O. and Emmanuel, D. O. (2024). Responsiveness and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Research Journal of Marketing and Allied Studies,12(1), 42-58*.

Awah A. E. (2015). Insurance Marketing in Tropical Issues in Marketing Vol. I.P. 198-213.

International Journal of Management Communication

Volume 12 Issue 4, October-December 2024

ISSN: 2836-5844

Impact Factor: 5.58

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/IJMC/index>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

- Awah, A.E., Akpan, A.O. and Eno, N.A. (2021). Pull promotion in the marketing of bank services: among microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, *Advance Journal of Economics and Marketing Research*, 4(9), 1-15
- Awah, A.E, Akpan, A.O. and Sampson, E.A. (2021). Public relations and savings mobilizations drive of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Advance. Journal of Economic and Marketing Research*, 6(7), 11-16
- Awah, A.E., Akpan, A.O. and Ele, L.E. (2021). Personal selling and saving mobilization drive of Uniuoyo Microfinance bank. *International Journal of Research in Finance and Marketing*, 11(10), 1-9
- Etuk, A., Awah, E.A. and Akpan O.A. (2020). E-Markting and savings mobilization drive of selected Microfinanace banks in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom state. *An international journal of Business Marketing and Management*.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A.O. and Awah, A.E. (2022). Factors influencing the adoption of mobile apps among young people in Nigeria. A study of University of Uyo students, *European Journal of Business and Management*, 14(3), 65-73
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2022). E-marketing Strategies and savings mobilization drive of selected microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, *International Journal of Business, Marketing and Management*, 7(3), 1-6
- Etuk, S.G., Udo I.S. and Awah A. (2022), Customer relationship management and marketing technology, Stra Mark communication consult
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah,A.E. (2023).Electronic banking and marketing performance of deposit money banks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. *American Interdisciplinary Journal of Business and Economics (AIJBE)*, 10(3), 23-42. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8346738>
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Physical ambience and Customer behavior in selected microfinance banks in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, *Top American Journal of marketing*.9(1), 1-24.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A. E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Assurance and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *American journal of information technology and management*, 12(2),1-23.

International Journal of Management Communication(IJMC)

<https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/IJMC/index>, Email: contact@americaserial.com

International Journal of Management Communication

Volume 12 Issue 4, October-December 2024

ISSN: 2836-5844

Impact Factor: 5.58

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/IJMC/index>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). E-service reliability and customer loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria: The moderating role of age and education, *Journal of current research in business and management sciences*, 12(2), 2-16.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Empathy and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Marketing Research and Brand Management*,12(2),36-50.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). The role of age and education in moderating the relationship between e-service security and customer loyalty: The Nigerian online shopping experience, *Michigan International Journal of Marketing. New Media and Communication*,12(2), 50-64.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A. E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Tangibility and customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Business and Cooperative Research*,9(2), 1-19.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). E- Service responsiveness and customer loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria: The moderating role of age and education, *European Journal of Marketing and Management Sciences*, 7(2), 13-30.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Internal marketing strategies and employee performance of commercial banks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, *American research journal of economics, finance and management*, 12 (3), 47-65.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). E-Service fulfillment and customer loyalty in online shopping in Nigeria: The moderating role of age and education, *British international journal of business and marketing research*, 7(4), 41-59.
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Marketing communication and consumer behaviour of betting firms in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *Advanced journal of economics and business research*, 12(3), 17-34.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah, A. E. (2024). Digital transformation service marketing in Nigeria; Reshaping strategies and enhancing customer engagement, *Michigan journal of multidisciplinary research*, 12(3), 29-45.

International Journal of Management Communication

Volume 12 Issue 4, October-December 2024

ISSN: 2836-5844

Impact Factor: 5.58

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/IJMC/index>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

- Davidow, M. (2021). The effectiveness of complaint management: A study of customer loyalty, *Journal of service marketing*, 35(4), 486-495
- Ladhari, R., Souiden, N. and Dufour, B. (2022). Customer complaint management: How does it influence customer satisfaction? *Journal of retailing and consumer services*, 66, 102890
- Nigerian communications commission, (2023). Annual telecommunication report 2023, Retrieved from (NCC Website).
- Nicholas, C., Arnaud, G. and Tanguy, R. (2022). An analysis of complaints in the smart phone market: Causes and consequences, *Journal of business research*, 143, 135-146.
- Statista. (2023). Smart phone market revenue worldwide from 2012 to 2023. Retrieve from (Statista Website).
- Udonde, U.E, Akpan, A.O. and Awah, A.E. (2022). Internal marketing and employee performance in insurance industry in Nigeria, *British, International Journal of Business and Marketing Research*, 5(1), 1-22.
- Udonde, U.E., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2022). Effect of communication and empowerment on sales-force performance in the Nigerian insurance industry. *Advance Journal of Economic and Marketing Research*, 7(11).
- Udoh, I.S., Josph, U.E. and Awah, A. (2022). Service Experience and passengers' patronage of transit companies in the south-south region of Nigeria. *British Journal*.